

PARENTS' INVOLVEMENT STRATEGIES AND PUPILS' PERFORMANCE IN UNIVERSAL PRIMARY EDUCATION SCHOOLS IN UGANDA: A CASE STUDY OF SELECTED UPE SCHOOLS IN AGAGO DISTRICT

Kidega Charles¹, Awila George², Kargo Moses³, Luyeye Makindu Bob⁴

ZHEJIANG NORMAL UNIVERSITY, COLLEGE OF EDUCATION, CHINA

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Abstract: The purpose of this study was to assess the influence of parents' involvement strategies on pupil performance in UPE schools in the Agago district. The theme of this study was considered significant because the findings of this study may benefit the government of Uganda in identifying better parental involvement strategies to improve pupil performance in UPE schools. The objective was; to assess the influence of the provision of a supportive study environment at home on pupil performance in selected UPE schools in Agago district. To deliver answers to the above empirical objectives, the study adopted a case study design where qualitative data were collected from 45 respondents. The document analysis and the Focus Group Discussions were used as methods of data collection. The findings of the study revealed that; parents' involvement strategies have a positive significant influence on pupil performance in UPE schools in terms of attendance rates, completion rates, quality of test scores obtained, and level of participation in co-curricular activities. The provision of a supportive study environment at home, parent-school communication, and parent presence at School, collectively account for the change in pupil performance in UPE schools. The study concluded that the active provision of a supportive study environment at home has a positive relationship with pupil's academic performance. Based on the study results, the study recommended that the Agago district administration should involve parents much more in school activities then they will realize better pupil performance in UPE schools in Agago district.

Keywords: Parents' involvement strategies, Pupils' performance, Universal Primary Education.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Introduction

Pupil performance is a key element in ensuring effective pupil learning and a key indication of whether the learning outcomes are being achieved. It is critical because the level of success learners attain has broad connotations for their future individual and professional lives. As the ardent goes the young generation is today's hope for a better tomorrow, any country's future lies in the hands of its young population. The family is the epitome of a child's socialization; thus, the parents are tasked to oversee their children's education. Schools should therefore develop strategies that promote parental involvement to improve student achievement. The study therefore assessed the influence of parents' involvement strategies on pupil performance in UPE schools in Agago District.

1.2 Theoretical Background

There are various learning performance theories, models, or frameworks associated with the assertion that parents' involvement has important implications on pupil performance. According to research, it is observed that students' success in school is greatly dependent on parents' involvement in their education. The school's role therefore is to develop strategies that promote parental involvement to improve student achievement. This research was however underpinned by Epstein's model (2001, 2011) of school, family, and community partnerships.

As a way of analyzing parent involvement strategies in school settings, Epstein's model is based on "the theory of overlapping spheres of home, school, and community influences". This model recognizes that parents participate in their children's education and may shape children's learning and development both at school and at home. The model proposes six types of parent involvement strategies that can promote parents' engagement in their child's education. These would however be examined at a later stage.

Several studies have adopted the theory. This model was applied by Mr. Miller while reviewing the school's mission to ascertain whether ability grouping was aligned with the mission; select an alternative that reflected the mission, and determine what action, if any, Principal Miller was to take to illustrate his leadership traits of fairness, equity, dignity and respect of persons. Guided by Standard 3, Principal Miller involved families and other stakeholders in the decision-making process to select and utilize a group decision technique that integrated hearing the opinions and views of the groups of parents, as well as other individuals and groups.

The model is criticized for being largely school-based and Euro-centric, however, research indicates that the model has influenced policy design and implementation of parent involvement programs. Epstein's framework therefore perfectly applies to this study due to its appreciation of various dimensions such as: at school and at home parents' involvement strategies in pupils' performance which are precursors in child performance at school.

1.3 Contextual background

The Education (Pre-Primary, Primary, and Post-Primary) Act 2008, defines the responsibilities of stakeholders namely; Government, parents and guardians, and the foundation bodies, in education and training. For purposes of this study, however, only the responsibilities of the parents and guardians were examined. In line with the education and training of the learners, the Act provides for the responsibilities of the parents and guardians namely: enrolling school going age children at school, provision of parental guidance and psychosocial welfare, food, clothing, shelter, medical care, and transport; promotion of discipline, moral, spiritual and cultural growth; participation in community support to school development and review of the school curriculum.

The significant increase in primary school enrolment from 2.95 million pupils in Government primary schools in 1996 to 5.09 million pupils in 1997 at the introduction of UPE, and now 7.10 million pupils in 2017 (UPE, 2019) following the advent of UPE indicates that payment of tuition fees and PTA charges deterred easy access to education in public schools, majorly for the less advantaged parents. This was because the UPE program was neither completely "free" nor "compulsory" primary education. The government was compelled to ask the parents to provide for their children's school clothing, a packed meal to eat while at school, and scholastic materials like pens and exercise books. The government, on the other hand, took responsibility for infrastructure, development and maintenance, instructional materials, examination fees, and teachers' salaries.

Similarly, Agago district has since the inception of UPE registered a massive increment in enrolment of pupils to 85%, especially the underprivileged children. This is in addition to improvement in infrastructure in terms of construction of classrooms and teachers' quarters. In the year 2010, pupils' enrolment was at 8,533 representing 4,043 boys and 4,490 girls respectively, while in the same year at least 149 classroom blocks, 168 toilet stances, and 22 staff units were constructed and 559 three-seater desks were procured. In 2018 pupils' enrolment was at 8,513 representing 4,043 boys and 4,470 girls respectively, and in the same year at least 57 classroom blocks and 20 staff units were constructed and 347 three-seater desks were procured.

1.4 Statement of the Problem

There is a growing concern in Agago district that in most UPE schools there is rampant absenteeism, late coming, and pupils' failure to have lunch at school. This trend has been associated with parents' failure to provide children with basic

requirements and the negative attitude of parents toward school programs thus, a tendency by parents to relegate their obligations and responsibilities postulated in the Education (*Pre-Primary, Primary, and Post-Primary*) Act 2008. (Agago district Report on **Facts on Performance in PLE 2022**, dated 20 February 2023).

Since the inception of UPE between 1997 and 2018, Agago District has registered a massive increment in enrolment of pupils in Primary One to 89%, especially the underprivileged children, but to the contrary has experienced a high drop-out rate as evidenced by the low completion rate in Primary Seven. Similarly, the district has persistently recorded poor PLE results whereby first grades have only oscillated between 19-24%. Furthermore, it has been indicated that out of 500 pupils enrolled in at least four selected UPE schools in Primary One in the year 2016, only 250 pupils sat for PLE exams in the year 2019, giving a completion rate of 58.2%.

Attempts by the District Council to address the above by putting in place several strategies, such as; conducting annual evaluation of pupils' academic performance and sharing performance reports with the parents, introduction of academic days to enable parents to discuss the progress of their children, conducting continuous assessments, strengthening monitoring and supervision by resident tutors, support to continuous professional development (CPD) and strengthening communication with community/parents through PTA and annual general meetings and home visits have been put in place. Yet, amidst these interventions, the same challenges still prevail, as evidenced by poor PLE results. It is worthwhile to note that if poor pupil performance is not addressed, little progress on achieving the quality Education for All (EFA) goals may not be realized. (UNEB, 2012; UWEZO, 2013).

1.5 Significance of the Study

The study was aimed at providing information to guide stakeholder engagement in designing parents' involvement strategies in learner performance and the effective implementation of UPE. Specifically, the study findings were intended to generate the following implications for schools, policymakers, and other researchers:

For schools; results of the study could provide insights to schools in developing learner-friendly policies that enhance parents' involvement strategies specifically; the establishment of clear communication channels between schools and parents including the use of new communication and information technologies; engagement of parents to actively get involved in the learning of their children; staff training programs and parents' meetings.

For policymakers; **the** results of the study could help policymakers offer clear guidance on developing explicit and relevant policies to provide direction on parents' involvement strategies to enable parents to become productively engaged in schools for effective learner performance.

Other Researchers; little is still known about the success of explicit parents' involvement strategies and learner performance. Therefore, the results of this study could be used as orientation data for other scholars and may divulge useful concepts to enrich linked studies.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Review

The magnitude of parents' involvement has important parents' engagement has implications for pupil excellence. Research has pointed out that it is the primary task of parents to offer children education in preparation for life challenges. This study attempts to review several learning performance theories, models, or frameworks that add value to this assertion namely:

Epstein's model (2001, 2011), proposes six types of parent involvement strategies namely; obligations of the family, such as the provision of basic needs like health and safety; school obligations such as communication between school and family; involvement in learning activities at home such as volunteering and at the school such as assisting teachers in the classroom or attending school events; involvement in decision making such as helping children with homework; governance, and advocacy and collaboration, such as serving in a parent-teacher association (PTA), on committees, or in other leadership positions; and exchanges with community organizations such as making connections with organizations that share responsibility for children's education, such as after school programs, health services, and other resources. Despite the inadequacies of this model such as being largely school-based and Euro-centric, research however indicates that this model has influenced policy design and implementation of parent involvement programs. Epstein's framework has been applied in the USA in testing the level of parents' involvement. For instance, in some States, Title I reports in schools provide for a portion of parent involvement. In addition, the model does not take into consideration factors that could inhibit parent

involvement such as income and literacy levels therefore the need for a more studies for an in-depth appreciation of such pre-suppositions. This framework can therefore be applied to this study due to its appreciation of various aspects of at-school and home parents' involvement in pupils' performance. The Researcher therefore seeks to apply this model in examining parent involvement strategies in UPE schools in the district

Epstein, (2001) discussed several school strategies that could get parents involved and these include: providing parents a voice; inspiring families to learn together; warranting parental involvement for full integration into schools' development plans; a pro-active methodology involving an action team of teachers and members of the community; school-initiated methodologies rather than school-centric approaches; schools reaching out to parents and the community initiatives coming from the school; interpositions that focus on the whole family. These strategies need to be assessed for their suitability and applicability.

However, other proponents such as Smit, (2007), contend that parent involvement strategies should be concerned with realizing the following: advancing a vision for parent involvement;

Additional theories and models were examined as below:

Walberg's (1981) Theory of Educational Productivity; seeks to obtain consensus regarding the "most significant influences on learning" and an analysis of research syntheses and surveys based on a widespread analysis and incorporation of over 3,000 studies and content of 179 handbook chapters and 91 reviews is made. of the 28 categories that identified learning influences, 11 were found to be the most influential domains, and among them was parental support. 8 involved social-emotional influences while others were found to be distant background influences and therefore less influential. The research concluded that "the direct intervention in the psychological determinants of learning promise the most effective avenues for reform". Much as the theory cites parental support among the influential variables involved in social-emotional influences on learning, it does not define the way the design and implementation of parent involvement programs significantly and positively affect pupil outcomes thus the need for more elaborative insights to fill up this gap through conducting such a study.

SCT: This theory suggests that "children engross messages about suitable behavior and socially accepted goals by witnessing and speaking to people significant to them" argues Bandura (1977). The study draws its conclusion from this assumption that parents can positively shape learners' attitudes and behaviors toward academic outcomes. Based on this theory, several developed countries including the USA have conducted research indicating that parents' involvement plays an important role in the children's academic success. Findings indicated that children learn to academically excel in school when their guardians/parents demonstrate an interest in their children's school work or hold them accountable for the completion of school assignments. In addition, the study was in agreement that, the less active children value school when parents actively demonstrate involvement in school activities. The theory however seems to base its findings among more affluent communities in making conclusions thus the need for a comparative study to validate the assumptions of the theory.

2.2 Related Review

Benefits, challenges, and limitations to parent involvement were examined below:

There are several benefits associated with parent involvement strategies and learner performance, namely; ensuring quality education services for children and promotion of educational and skill gains. Parents have a responsibility to participate and also ensure that learners are participating in school activities. Parents in this regard should therefore be encouraged to immensely contribute to the learning process by fulfilling their responsibilities such as volunteering at school, providing meals, supporting children to do their homework, and taking up leadership positions on school governing bodies (Epstein, 1991:63).

Understanding factors that may inhibit parent involvement is still an area of interest for research. Hill N.E, (2003) in his study "parent-school involvement and school performance" established that there are other influences associated with parent involvement, and these include features such as age, sex, family income occupation, and educational attainment. Factors such as occupation, and family income also imply that parent involvement is closely associated with parent empowerment. As noted by Larry Ferlazzo in his article "Involvement or engagement?" parent empowerment involves identifying their needs, and projects, and goals to enable them to effectively contribute. This calls for taking stock of parents' concerns through taking care of their expectations. Parent involvement calls for the provision of resources to parents, allowing them to get involved in school activities, and facilitating them to oversee their children's progression. Then,

establish partnerships with them by setting targets for their learners and diverse means to reinforce the classroom. This therefore implies that parents should as much as possible be engaged in the learning process.

Research studies dedicated to parents' involvement in pupils' performance have intensely pointed to the view that parents' concern for their children's learning promotes the improvement of attitudes necessary for success. The view that parent engagement impacts the academic excellence of learners is not only shared by researchers, however, also policymakers. This has influenced the integration of parent involvement programs and activities into broader educational policy initiatives (Alameda-Lawson, 2010). It was however important to further enrich findings from studies to draw conclusions that could inform policy.

Much as parents' involvement strategies in school are positively linked with academic outcomes, including grades, classroom behavior, pupils' aspirations, and school completion, (Hill, N. E., & Taylor, L. C., 2004), however, other studies indicate that contact with the school on pupil performance trails, school arrangement and socio-emotional modification, and Mathematics and reading scores present a negative effect. Research indicates that this negative influence was a result of inadequate communication between parents and schools. However, these findings do not take into consideration other factors that may influence parent involvement strategies such as their socioeconomic status.

Research conducted in the United States suggests positive helpful implications on educational outcomes, including grades, classroom behavior, and pupils' aspirations and school completion, but fewer studies suggest negative effects. Also, findings of a national survey conducted in the USA on high school pupils presented a negative influence of parents' involvement strategies at home on pupil performance, particularly among immigrant and minority pupils. However, these findings needed to be cross-examined to identify the missing link by conducting further research.

Smit, (2007), contends that several influences could inhibit or challenge parent engagement and these include: scanty facts to parents about the intentions and processes of the school that could promote parent engagement; work obligations and demands care for other children, and inadequate time; inability to participate due to communication obstructions, inadequate understanding of what constitutes parent involvement, stereotyping and a feeling by parents of being unappreciated and marginalized, teachers discouraging parent-started contact, and welcoming contact when they start it. Other influences may include intimidation of parents by schools, parents' negative school experiences, unwelcome or uncomfortable behaviors by the schools, and a feeling of parents' perceived overstepping of their role at school. Such concerns could create confusion and strains in the promotion of effective parent engagement. It was critical, therefore, to address these likely obstacles to parent commitment by expounding roles to ensure reasonable and pooled understandings during the design of parent involvement strategies.

Much as these presuppositions closely associate parent involvement strategies with increased learners' academic performance, it was important to fully understand the explicit mechanisms through which parent involvement influences a child's performance. Therefore, researching the subject matter would inform further research and policy initiatives and would lead to the development of more effective intervention programs designed to increase parent involvement and pupil performance. This study therefore rooted in further appreciation of the various prepositions linking parents' involvement strategies and pupil performance.

2.3 Conceptual Review

Influence of parents' involvement strategies on pupil performance: Larry Ferlazzo, in his article "Involvement or engagement?" underscores several parent involvement strategies that influence pupil performance. First, by enhancing parent-school communication. Ferlazzo contends that "a school striving for parent engagement, tends to lead with its ears thereby listening to what parents think, dream, and worry about." Second by promoting active parents' presence at school through inviting them to activities and partnering with them to set goals for their students. Then, providing a supportive study environment by providing parents with resources, helping them monitor their children's progress, and finding ways to strengthen the classroom. Parents' involvement strategies at home therefore include; Parents guiding the child to do the reading, discussing school events with the child, and helping the child to do homework. In addition, Parents' involvement strategies at school include; attending school events and functions or volunteering in classrooms. Therefore, to meaningfully involve parents, Schools ought to engage parents, regularly communicate with them, and ensure that Parents become part and partial of the child's learning process.

A critical need for further research: As observed by Hill & Craft, (2003), this study roots for further appreciation of the various prepositions linking parent involvement and pupil performance. The study roots for further research so that specific

mechanisms through which parent involvement exerts its influence on a child's performance are fully understood (Hill & Craft, 2003). Therefore, an in-depth understanding of the likely mechanisms would provide a basis for further research and the development of policy initiatives thus the development of more effective intervention programs designed to increase parent involvement and pupil performance.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a case study design employing qualitative research. The case study was used as it saves time and money and given the purpose as well as the research questions to be used, it was hoped that the data collected would be adequate to answer the research questions. The use of qualitative methods on the other hand was employed to ensure high internal and external validity of the findings of the study.

3.1 Study Population

To achieve the study objectives as highlighted in Chapter One, the participants were selected from among the parents and pupils as direct participants and teachers, Teachers, and the Agago district Inspector of schools as indirect participants. The researcher purposively selected pupils from Primary six (P.6) to participate in the study because these students were expected to have been in the school for more than five years and were presumed to have attained the desired level of literacy and numeracy compared to the lower classes and therefore stood a better chance of providing useful information. The study targeted Parents of the UPE pupils from the four selected primary schools implementing the UPE program in Agago district with specific attention to Lira Palwo, Lacek, Obolokome, and Wimunu pecek primary schools from each school, pupils and parents of the 05 best and worst performers in Primary six (P.6) respectively. The head teachers and class teachers of P.6 of the selected schools were targeted to provide data about the school and students' academic scores and reports upon which data was analyzed. Finally, Lira Palwo, Lacek, Obolokome, and Wimunupecek primary schools of schools were selected to be part of the study to provide data about schools about the overall performance of the schools in the district

3.2 Sample size

Based on the hypothesis that parents' involvement has a significant influence on pupil performance, the study interacted with parents of the four (04) selected UPE pupils in Agago District held an FGD with the pupils, Head-teachers, and teachers, and analyzed the baseline data collected. The target population included; parents, and pupils from four (04) selected UPE schools in the Agago district. The sample population 49 of participants was drawn from parents, pupils, teachers, head teachers, and the Agago district (Education Department). The target population includes 40 parents, 04 teachers, 04 head teachers, and 01 District staff/ education department who were key informants.

3.3 Sampling techniques and procedure

3.3.1 Census

The researcher used the Census technique because it's a versatile tool in the process of education and examination of the consequences of education on individuals' life chances (Arikunto, 2011). Upon getting the names of the pupils, and their class mark performances in each of the selected classes (P.7), these pupils were stratified along those lines and each given a number. A census sample of 05 fast and slow learners whose numbers were selected had a focus group discussion with the researcher.

3.3.2 Purposive sampling

The elements selected for the sample were purposively selected on the judgment of the Researcher to obtain a representative sample by using a sound judgment. The Researcher sought this method to save time and money. The Researcher purposively selected parents of the fast and slow learners to obtain a representative sample for conducting the FGDs. Head-teachers as well as P.7 class teachers of the participating schools were purposively selected on the assumption that they were the very people from whom the information about the participating schools was obtained. Finally, to validate the information obtained from the participating schools in this study area, the District Inspector of schools was purposively selected.

3.4 Data Collection Methods

3.4.1 Documents literature review

The researcher reviewed existing secondary documents originating from the schools. The documents were reviewed which were related to parents' involvement strategies on pupil performance in UPE schools in Agago District. This method was less costly, more accurate, and covered a long period.

3.4.2 Focus Group Discussion Method

As Mr Okello Patrick (2021) put it, the Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) are appropriate for qualitatively getting a ‘group story’ about parents’ involvement strategies on pupil performance in UPE schools in the district council. Focus group discussions were used to collect qualitative data from the respondents. This was particularly applied to the administration staff namely; Head-teachers and teachers, parents and pupils. This method was considered because it allowed the researcher and the respondents to seek some clarifications to better understand each other (Malunda, et al., 2021).

4. ANALYSIS, PRESENTATION AND INTERPRETATION

Response Rate

Out of 49 participants sampled, only 45 engaged in a FGD making 91. % response rate which is greater than 70% deemed representative of an investigation (Sekaran, 2019). The high response rate was dependent on the four active Research Assistants deployed in the field for data collection.

Instrument	Target Responses	Actual Responses	Response Rate (%)
Focus group discussion	49	45	91
Total	49	45	91

Source: Primary source

Table 4.1, Those who participated in the FGD were (91%) of the sampled population. Consequently, the study attained a reasonable and acceptable sample to collect adequate and vital information to investigate the influence of supportive study environment, effective parent-school communication, active Parents Presence at School, and Pupil performance in selected UPE schools in Agago district (Sekaran, 2019).

Demographic characteristics of the participants

The demographic information of interest to the study was only the sex of the pupils.

Variable	Category	Freq	Percent (%)
Sex	Males	23	46.9
	Females	26	53.1
Total		49	100%

Source: Primary source

In terms of Sex, many of the participants were male taking the highest portion of 26(53.1%) and 23(46.9%) were female participants. The result can be interpreted that the views of both female and male pupils were represented in this study. The results also suggest that the two categories (females and males) in this study were fully represented and catered for.

Empirical Findings.

Qualitative analysis of pupil performance

The significance of this subsection is aimed at increasing the overall understanding of the quality, characteristics, and meanings of the researched work on pupil performance in selected UPE schools in the district. The significance of this section is to help the study in determining the particular frequency of traits or characteristics, allowing the researcher to form parameters through which the data set could be observed. The qualitative data collection method used in this study was focus group discussions in which participants were grouped into 4-6 participants and the researcher was the moderator for ongoing discussion. The following were some of the responses obtained on pupil performance in selected UPE schools in the district during the focus discussion.

As regards whether the pupils’ completion rate has improved in the school, a participant coded as ADC-07 had this to say:

“...the completion rates of our pupils in the school have deteriorated gravely”

The above statement seems to reveal that some participants refuted that the pupils’ completion rate has improved in the UPE schools in Agago district.

Concerning improvement in Co-curricular activities in school, a participant coded as ADC-02 had this to say:

“...co-curricular activities are very minimal in the school. It’s almost not on the school time table”

The above declaration reveals that some participants refuted the statement that there is improvement in Co-curricular activities in school.

As regards whether the class attendance rates have improved, one participant in the FDG coded as ADC-04 had this to say:

“...pupil attendance rates have gradually dropped year in and out. Partly, this is because pupils are not supposed to be punished for failure to attend school and some educators are not bothered so much about pupil’s performance in class”

The above account seems to reveal that some participants contested that there is improvement in Co-curricular activities in UPE schools in Agago district.

Qualitative analysis of Supportive study environment at home

The significance of this section is to increase the overall understanding of the quality, characteristics, and meanings of the research worked in a supportive study environment at home. The following were some of the responses obtained on the Supportive study environment at home and their interpretation.

As regards whether teachers conduct home visits to know the child’ background, one participant coded as AD-03 had this to say:

“...hahaha...that is history. I have never seen any teacher coming to my home to ensure she/he follows up the child’s background”. “...I believe this could be partly the source of poor academic performance of some pupils”.

The above statement reveals that some participants disagreed that teachers conduct home visits to know the child’s background.

As to whether the children are provided with some study educational videos to stimulate and enhance their performance, outcomes reveal that many of the participants refuted this statement. One participant coded as AD-08 had this to say:

“Resources (money) are merger, I cannot afford to purchase child study videos when urgent matters like Rent and food are waiting for me”

The above statement seems to reveal that some participants agreed that they do not provide some study educational videos to stimulate and enhance the performance of their children while at home.

5. SUMMARY, DISCUSSION, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Supportive study environment at home and pupil performance

Informed by the results of this study, the findings revealed that teachers rarely conduct home visits to know the children’s background. This indicates that the majority of the teachers do not demonstrate their support for pupils’ families. Teacher home visits are an avenue in which teachers show their support for pupils’ families. The teachers visit the home parameters where the family stays. This specifies a negative indicator in terms of pupils’ performance. Teacher home visits are important because it aims at parental involvement in education which is an important issue for governments and nongovernmental organizations in Uganda.

Furthermore, some of the key qualitative findings indicated that there isn’t a clear school policy on conducting home visits in most of the UPE schools in Agago district. Uganda has developed educational policies that point to parental involvement in education as an important issue for government and nongovernmental-aided schools. Poor socio-economic circumstances can impede the implementation of policies and parental involvement in education. The above qualitative findings revealed that indeed a supportive study environment at home has a positive influence on pupil performance in terms of attendance rates, completion rates, quality of test scores obtained, and level of participation in co-curricular activities. The findings further indicated a moderate positive and significant influence of a supportive study parameter at home on pupil performance. This infers that a positive increase in a supportive study environment at home will lead to positive pupil performance in terms of attendance rates, completion rates, quality of test scores obtained, and level of participation in co-curricular activities.

Based on these findings, it was inferred that once the Agago district emphasizes a supportive study environment at home in terms of conducting home visits, developing homework policies, and suggesting enrichment activities will improve pupil performance in terms of attendance rates, completion rates, quality of test scores obtained and level of participation in co-curricular activities.

Discussion of the findings

The overall purpose of the study was to assess the influence of parents' involvement strategies on pupil performance in UPE schools in the district. Based on the findings from both qualitative and quantitative results, the overall study findings established that parents' involvement strategies have a positive significant influence on pupil performance in UPE schools in the district. Having generated the overall purpose of the study, the discussion is based on the research objectives as stated hereunder.

Provision of a supportive study environment at home and pupil performance

Study objective one sought to assess the influence of the provision of a supportive study environment at home on pupil performance in selected UPE schools in Agago district. Findings indicated that a supportive study environment at home played a major role in pupil performance in Agago district. The findings showed that parents/guardians participate in monitoring how the children organize their homework while at home. Interviews conducted by the researcher confirmed this by noting in the words of one key participant, "I have always monitored how my children organize their homework".

Hill, (2003) agrees with the above view in the specific persuasion of pupil performance and indicates that factors such as occupation of the parent/guardian, and family income imply that parent involvement in most school activities is closely associated with pupil performance. Parent involvement calls for the provision of resources to parents, allowing them to get involved in school events, and facilitating them to observe their children's advances. Then, establish partnerships with them by setting targets for their learners and diverse ways to strengthen the classroom. This therefore implies that parents should as much as possible be engaged in the learning process.

The study established that parents/guardians allocate their children time to do their homework. Parents/guardians who take an active role in caring for their children's education are offering the support their children need to see success at school. For instance, parents/ guardians who allocate their children time to do their homework are showing their children that they care about their education and that it's important enough to deserve their attention resulting in pupil performance. These findings concur with Alameda-Lawson, (2010) research findings on children's performance, whose results revealed that learners' educational outcomes improve when parents are engaged in the children's education. This calls for taking stock of parents' concerns through taking care of their expectations.

Based on the synthesized literature, a supportive study environment at home positively influences pupil performance, but the challenge remains that "Teachers rarely conduct home visits to know the child's background". This phenomenon is likely to affect pupil performance in Agago district because of poor parent-teacher relationships.

Conclusions

The findings indicated that a supportive study environment at home has a significant influence on pupil performance. The study concluded that a supportive study environment at home has a significant positive influence on pupil performance. This means that improvements in a supportive study environment at home such as conducting home visits, developing homework policies, and suggesting enrichment activities shall have a significant positive contribution towards pupil performance at the district

Recommendations

The study recommends that a supportive study environment at home should further be encouraged and supported in terms of attention since it greatly contributes to better pupil performance in selected UPE schools in the Agago district. This could be done by giving the stakeholders some training in parent-child parenting workshops and seminars. The study believes that by having the above supportive study environment at home stimulation pathways in the district, there will be an improvement in pupil attendance rates, completion rates, quality of test scores obtained, and level of participation in co-curricular activities.

Further research

The study investigated the influence of Parents' involvement strategies on the Performance of UPE pupils in selected UPE schools in the Agago district. However, the study did not cover all possible areas surrounding the variables of the study (Parents' involvement strategies and pupil performance in selected UPE schools). This was attributed to the time constraint factor and financial dilemmas among others, which the researcher was facing. Ideally, the researcher proposes areas for further research to be undertaken in the following areas: The role of stakeholder participation and sustainability of UPE in selected schools in Agago district

Contribution of the study

Based on the results in the predecessor chapter, the study contributes to Parents' involvement strategies and pupil performance model. The study has drawn on the researchers' observations from the perceptibly disregarded area of provision of a supportive study environment at home, effective parent-school communication, and active parent presence at School in an "academic-business oriented environment". The study has tried to fill the gaps in previous literature about how parents' involvement strategies influence pupil performance, drawing experience from the Agago district. Therefore, this research report gives an insight into the influence of parents' involvement strategies and pupil performance by theoretical investigation. Also, through conducting empirical analysis, the present research report shows how Parents' involvement strategies influence pupil performance.

Thus, based on the qualitative findings generated in the predecessor chapter, this investigation caters to a supposed requirement of formulating new mechanisms for curbing mediocre pupil performance in Agago district. The statistics further provide Agago district administrators and participants with more useful knowledge in understanding parents' involvement strategies and pupil excellence, hence to say how to concern the parents' involvement strategies theory and change Parents' involvement strategies within the framework of management and academia to help in improving pupil performance.

REFERENCES

- [1] Alameda-Lawson, T. L. (2010). Social workers' roles in facilitating the collective involvement of low-income, culturally diverse parents in an elementary school.
- [2] Aldrete, N. (1999). Parental Involvement and Academic Performance of High School Students. Bacolod City: University of Negros Occidental-Recoletos.
- [3] Arikunto, S. (2011). *Prosedur Panellation: Suatu Pendekatan Praktek*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
- [4] Bandura. (1977). Self-efficacy: Toward a unifying theory of behavioral change. *Psychological Review* 1977; 84:191–215. [PubMed: 847061].
- [5] Barnard, W. M. (2004). Parent involvement in elementary school and educational attainment. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 26(1), 39-62.
- [6] Brief, P. (2006). Policy Brief No. 10. Kampala: Ministry of Education & Sports.
- [7] Christenson, S. L. (1997). Parents and school psychologists' perspectives on parent involvement activities. *School Psychology Review*, 26(1), 111-130.
- [8] Creswell, J. W. (2009). *Research design: qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approach*. Thousand Oaks, California: Sage Publications.
- [9] Epstein, J. L. (2001). *School, family, and community partnerships: Preparing educators and improving schools*. Westview: Boulder, CO.
- [10] Epstein, J. L. (2011). *School, family, and community partnerships: Preparing educators and improving schools*. (2nd ed.). Philadelphia, PA: Westview Press.
- [11] Goals. (2000). *Educate America Act, 1994*. p.3.
- [12] Henderson, A. &. (1994). *A new generation of evidence: the family is critical to student achievement*. Washington DC: National Committee for citizens in education.

- [13] Hill N.E, C. S. (2003). Parent-school involvement and school performance: Mediated pathways among socioeconomically comparable African American and Euro-American families. *Journal of Educational Psychology* 2003; 96: 74–83.
- [14] Hill, N. E. (2004). Parental school involvement and children’s pupil performance-Pragmatics and issues. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 13, 161–164.
- [15] Hill, N. E., & Taylor, L. C. (2004). Parental school involvement and children’s pupil performance-Pragmatics and issues. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 13, 161–164.
- [16] Hoover-Dempsey, K. V. (2005). 'Why do parents become involved? Research findings and implications. *The Elementary School Journal*, vol. 106, no.2, 105-130.
- [17] Khumalo, W. (2006). Parental involvement in classrooms in rural schools. Unpublished master's thesis. Johannesburg, South Africa.: University of Johannesburg,
- [18] Kothari, C. (2004). *Research methodology, methods, and techniques*. New Dheli.: New Age International.
- [19] Larry Ferlazzo, J. (2011, May). Involvement or Engagement? ASCD, pp. 10-14.
- [20] Lee, J.-S. &. (2006). Parent involvement, cultural capital, and the achievement gap among elementary school children. *American Educational Research Journal*, 43, 193- 218.
- [21] Malunda, P. N., Atwebembeire, J., & Sentamu, P. N. (2021). Research Supervision as an Antecedent to Graduate Student Progression in the Public Higher Institutions of Learning in Uganda. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 20(5).
- [22] Mambane, M. (1998). Parental involvement as an aspect of school management: Implication for whole school development. Unpublished master's thesis, University of Johannesburg, South Africa.
- [23] Manz, P. H. (2004). Multidimensional assessment of family involvement among urban elementary students. *Journal of School Psychology*, 42(6), 461- 475.
- [24] McCarthy, S. J. (2000). Home-school connections: A review of the literature. *Journal of Educational Research*, 93, 145-154.
- [25] NAPE. (2016). The achievement of learners in early grade reading in selected Districts of Uganda: Baseline Report, Kampala: Uganda National Examinations Board.
- [26] Schueler, B. (2014). Measuring family-school relations for school reform and improvement. Society for Research on Educational Effectiveness, Retrieved from:
- [27] <http://www.eric.ed.gov/contentdelivery/servlet/ERICServlet?accno=ED562821>
- [28] Smit, (2007). 'Types of parents and school strategies aimed at the creation of effective partnerships'. *International Journal about Parents in Education*, vol. 1, no. 0, pp. 45-52.
- [29] UNEB, U. N. (2012). National Assessment of Progress in Education: The achievement of primary school pupils in Uganda in numeracy and literacy in English. Kampala: UNEB.
- [30] UPE. (2019). Universal Primary Education, Transforming Uganda. Kampala: Ministry of Education & Sports.
- [31] UWEZO. (2013). “Are Our Children Learning? Literacy and Numeracy Across East Africa 2013”. Nairobi, Kenya: Uwezo East Africa at Tweezer.
- [32] Walberg, H. J. (1981). A theory of educational productivity. In F. H. Farley & N. Gordon (Eds.), *Psychology and education. The state of the union*. Berkeley, CA: McCutchan.
- [33] Webster. (1989). *Webster's Encyclopedic Unabridged Dictionary. Second Edition Revised*